

Some aspects of a chemical relationship. Kinetics and Analytical Chemistry in the service of each other^ψ

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Synopsis

(A) Contribution of Kinetics to Analytical Chemistry

- (1) Trace metal-ion catalysis and its determination kinetically
- (2) General metal-ion catalysis and its kinetic determination
- (3) Volumetric methods
- (4) Fe^{II} as a pre-reductor for the determination of H₂O₂ with Tl^{III}
- (5) Nature of acid monitoring the reactivity and course of a metal-ion reaction
- (6) Modification of known methods to suit a particular kinetic analysis
- (7) Iodine monochloride as a pre-oxidiser for sulphite estimation with permanganate

(B) Contribution of Analytical Chemistry to Kinetics (some aspects)

- (1) Greater role of Analytical Chemistry in the evaluation of mechanism
- (2) Existence of iodite
- (3) Complexes of increasing reactivity during a kinetic run
- (4) Unusual behavior of iodide with regard to catalysis in the peroxomonophosphoric acid and hydrazine reaction in acid solution
- (5) Unusual phenomenon of rate-increase during a kinetic run

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(A) Contribution of Kinetics to Analytical Chemistry

Kinetics is in the service of Analytical Chemistry in a big way, though reverse is also true to some extent. In fact the role of Analytical Chemistry in Kinetics is not only essential, but specific. No kinetics study can be made if there is no suitable method of analysis for following the kinetics and the first thing that a kineticist does, is to devise an analytical method which is free of interference of the species present in the system other than that which is being determined. Conditions are found which modify the already known method or altogether a new method is devised. There is one more aspect of the relationship of kinetics with Analytical Chemistry. A kinetics study carefully made but yielding irregular, unexpected and complicated results often lead to a method of analysis. It is

some of such situations that have been described in this article.

(1) Trace metal-ion catalysis and its determination

The trace metal-ions present in the reagents and distilled water, have a great mechanistic role by influencing the kinetics of redox reactions and this therefore has led to a greater understanding of the chemistry of these metal-ions. The role of such ions and others in inorganic redox reactions has been exhaustively described in an article¹. Many reactions which do not occur or are very slow, are catalysed by these trace metal-ion impurities present in the distilled water and the reagents. Such metal-ions are Fe^{III}, Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}, Os^{VIII} etc. in general and many others like Ru^{III}, Pt^{II}, Ag^I etc. in specific cases. The first conse-

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quence of their presence is that they make the kinetic results irreproducible, and therefore to obtain reproducibility in such a study, same samples of reagents and the same source of distilled water are employed. The B.D.H. AnalaR and E. Merck G.R. samples of CuSO_4 are different in their trace Fe^{III} impurity content. EDTA has been recommended to mask the effect of these metal-ions provided there are no other complications. Another significant fact that has emerged is that kinetics study of such solutions enables one to determine the trace metal-ion concentration. 1×10^{-9} molar concentration of Co^{II} catalyses the decomposition² of peroxomonosulphuric acid. 10^{-7} molar concentration of Cu^{II} is sufficient to catalyse many oxidations by peroxydisulphate³.

Oxidation of ascorbic acid (H_2A) by peroxodiphosphate (pdp)⁴ can occur with or without Cu^{II} and $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$ as shown in Fig. 1. The non-zero intercept of the figure at zero concentration of the catalysts shows that traces of these ions are present in the system. One can know the concentrations of these metal-ions in the system from absorption spectroscopy and since one also knows the reactivities (slopes of a plot of rate vs [metal-ion]) of these ions from a kinetic study, one can calculate the intercept by adding the two contributions. Table I gives the total amount of ($\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} + \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$) so calculated in a number of systems and they are of the same order of magnitude.

Fig. 1. Plot of initial rate vs $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}]$ (●) and $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]$ (○) at $[\text{H}_2\text{A}] = 3.0 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{pdp}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 3.9$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{temp.} = 35^\circ$. Atomic absorption spectroscopy gives $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}} = 8 \times 10^{-7}$ and $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} = 4 \times 10^{-7}$. Intercept calculated = $1.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Intercept found = $1.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Table I. Kinetic estimates of the impurities ($\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} + \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$) in the system from the intercept of a plot of rate vs [metal-ion]

Reaction	Catalyst	$10^7(\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} + \text{Fe}^{\text{III}})$ (Found)	pH	$t^{1/2}/C$	Ref
Ascorbic acid + O_2	Cu^{II}	5.0	3.45	25	5
Ascorbic acid + O_2	VO^{2+}	2.7	2.85	25	6
Ascorbic acid + O_2	UO_2^{2+}	3.0	1.02	25	7
Ascorbic acid + $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$	Cu^{II}	7.5	3.43	30	8
Ascorbic acid + Air	Cu^{II}	3.7	4.91	30	9
Ascorbic acid + $\text{P}_2\text{O}_8^{4-}$	Cu^{II}	4.0	3.90	35	4
$\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-} + \text{P}_2\text{O}_8^{4-}$	Fe^{III}	3.2	0.05	30	10

Catalysis by trace metal-ions is more obvious in the reactions involving hexacyanoferrate(II) and hexacyanoferrate(III). Catalysis by 10^{-8} molar Cu^{II} has been found in cystine¹¹ oxidation with $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$. Similarly oxidations of hydroxylamine¹² with $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ are catalysed by Cu^{II} and $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$. However, catalysis by these ions in peroxodiphosphate oxidation of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ is not simple¹³. Aquo and edta complexes have different roles and Cu^{II} -aquo inhibits the oxidation though Cu^{II} -edta complex catalyses. Following chart brings out the difference in catalysis by Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} in the form of aquo- and edta complexes in the oxidation of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ and the reduction of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ by suitable reagents.

Role of aquo- and edta complexes of Cu^{II} and Fe^{III} in $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}/\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ redox systems (based on the works of Refs. 11-13) :

The role of Fe^{III}/Fe^{II} as impurity in the distilled water and the reagents can be appreciated through equilibrium (1)¹⁰.

This equilibrium will operate when any oxidising reactant is slow to react with Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻ but reacts favourably with Fe²⁺. Similarly if a reducing agent reacting slowly with Fe(CN)₆³⁻ but quickly with Fe³⁺, it will reduce Fe(CN)₆³⁻ through this equilibrium. The equilibrium constant *K* determined spectrophotometrically was found to be 31 ± 16 at 28° and *I* = 0.05 *M* and [H⁺] = 0.01 *M*. The value is highly susceptible to changes in ionic strength, hydrogen-ion concentration and the presence of Cu^{II} as impurity in the system. Aquo-Cu^{II} shifts the equilibrium to left since another equilibrium (2) becomes operative and Fe(CN)₆³⁻ reacts with Cu^I. If one calculates the rate constant (*k*₁₂) for the (Fe³⁺ + Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻) reaction of equilibrium (1) from the Marcus equation¹⁴.

$$k_{12} = (k_{11} k_{22} K_{12})^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

(where *k*₁₁ and *k*₂₂ are isotopic exchange rate constants for Fe³⁺/Fe²⁺ and Fe(CN)₆⁴⁻/Fe(CN)₆³⁻ couples respectively, and *K*₁₂ is the equilibrium constant for equilibrium (1)), one obtains 2 × 10³ M⁻¹ s⁻¹ for it which is comparable to the experimental value of 6.5 × 10³ M⁻¹ s⁻¹ at 28°. This only supports the existence and operation of equilibrium (1) and also the presence of Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺ as impurity in the distilled water. All values of the constants were experimental as mentioned in the paper¹⁰.

(2) General metal-ion catalysis and its kinetic determination

The problem of trace metal-ions and their possible elimination is a necessity in the study of Kinetics, but the catalysis by the metal-ions in reactions in general is a subject which has received due attention in the study of Kinetics. Since in most cases the rate dependence on the catalyst is simple, there has always been a possibility to determine the metal-ion concentration in a sample by a kinetic method. All one needs is the appropriate rate law and the rate constants and determine the rate of a particular reaction in the presence of catalyst-sample. Several hundred such reactions involving different types, have been studied kinetically and the concentration determined. However, there is a great limitation in making use of

such kinetic methods for determining metal-ion concentration since the method is time consuming and is very susceptible to the presence of unspecified and unknown impurities in the sample. Some of the examples taken from a book¹⁵, with reactions and the catalyst employed along with their sensitivities, are given in Table 2. This method of analysis could never become of use for reasons stated above and it is only of academic interest to know the catalysis of various metal-ions and their sensitivities in influencing the kinetics of a particular reaction.

(3) Volumetric methods

The biggest contribution of Kinetics to Analytical Chemistry is the fact that enables one to use the kinetic results in devising volumetric methods to determine the constituent under question. The reaction between peroxodiphosphate and iodide is slow¹⁶ but it can be made fast by employing Cu^{II} and Fe^{III}/Fe^{II} as catalysts in acid solution and large concentration of iodide so that peroxodiphosphate may be determined iodometrically¹⁷. Catalysis is said to operate through the following mechanism.

Oxidations of Cu^I and Fe^{II} are known to be fast.

Investigation¹⁸ of the behaviour of peroxydisulphate in increasing amount of conc. H₂SO₄ led one to determine peroxydisulphate in about 5.0 *M* H₂SO₄ as peroxomonosulphuric acid iodometrically and in about 6.5 *M* H₂SO₄ as H₂O₂ with permanganate¹⁹. Following reactions are said to occur.

This method of determination could not become popular because it is inconvenient to use H₂SO₄ in such large concentration.

Table 2. Catalytic reactions, catalyst and sensitivities of their determination in the catalysed reactions

Reaction	Catalysts	Sensitivity $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for underlined elements
$4\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} = 2\text{SO}_4^{2-} + 2\text{H}^+ + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Tl, Zr, Th, <u>Mo</u> , V, W, Ta	6×10^{-3}
$\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + 2\text{I}^- + 2\text{H}^+ = \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{I}_2$	Zr, Hf, Th, <u>Mo</u> , Ta, Fe, W	2×10^{-2}
$2\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 = 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2$	<u>Cu</u> , Fe, Pd	2×10^{-3}
	<u>Mn</u>	1×10^{-4}
$\text{ClO}_3^- + 6\text{I}^- + 6\text{H}^+ = \text{Cl}^- + \text{H}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Re, <u>V</u> , Ru	2×10^{-2}
	<u>Os</u>	4×10^{-4}
$\text{BrO}_3^- + \text{organic reducing compounds}$	<u>V</u> , Mo	1×10^{-3}
$\text{IO}_3^- + \text{organic aromatic amines}$	<u>Mn</u> , V	1×10^{-4}
$\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} + \text{phenetidine}$	<u>Ag</u> , Mn	2×10^{-6}
$2\text{MnO}_4^- + 5\text{HAsO}_2 + \text{H}^+ = 2\text{Mn}^{2+} + 5\text{AsO}_3^- + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	<u>Os</u>	1.0
$2\text{Fe}^{3+} + 2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} = 2\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{S}_4\text{O}_6^{2-}$	<u>Cu</u>	2×10^{-1}
$2\text{Fe}^{3+} + 2\text{CNS} = 2\text{Fe}^{2+} + (\text{CNS})_2$	<u>I</u>	1×10^{-5}
$\text{Ag}^+ + \text{Fe}^{2+} = \text{Ag} + \text{Fe}^{3+}$	Au	1×10^{-6}
$\text{Ce}^{4+} + \text{HAsO}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} = 2\text{Ce}^{3+} + 2\text{H}^+ + \text{HAsO}_3$	<u>Os</u>	0.3
	<u>I</u>	1×10^{-2}
$\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-} + 3\text{bipy} = \text{Fe}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+} + 6\text{CN}^-$	<u>Ag</u>	2×10^{-2}
$\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-} + 3\text{phen} = \text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3^{2+} + 6\text{CN}^-$	<u>Hg</u>	2×10^{-1}
$2\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{PO}_2^- + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} = 2\text{Ni} + \text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 + 3\text{H}^+$	Ru, Os, <u>Pd</u> , Pt	1.5×10^{-3}

In an attempt to follow the kinetics of the oxidation of ascorbic acid⁴ with peroxodiphosphate by estimating the former, led one to a volumetric method²⁰ for the determination of ascorbic acid with Tl^{III} in HClO_4 solution using *p*-ethoxychrysoidine as indicator. Indirect determination by employing excess Tl^{III} and estimating unreacted Tl^{III} iodometrically, can also be made. In this way ascorbic acid in vitamin C, fruits, vegetables etc. can be easily determined. The same method enables one to determine²¹ thiourea, thiosulphate and sulphite with the following stoichiometries.

(4) Fe^{II} as a pre-reductor for the determination of H_2O_2 with Tl^{III}

Sometimes being a keen observer of one's own mistake is greatly rewarding. The reaction of Tl^{III} and H_2O_2 is slow²². The high pseudo-catalytic activity of Fe^{II} was discovered accidentally during attempts to follow the kinetics of the reaction by estimating peroxide cerimetrically in the presence of excess of chloride ion ($\gg [\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]$).

Excess Ce^{IV} was added to the aliquots of the reaction mixture at pre-determined times and unreacted Ce^{IV} was back titrated with Fe^{II} . Such a procedure did not yield consistent and reproducible results on account of traces of Fe^{II} left over in the titration vessel if not properly cleaned before the next titration. Fe^{II} initiated a fast reaction between Tl^{III} and H_2O_2 . A systematic work indicated that 10^{-7} molar Fe^{II} brings about completion of Tl^{III} - H_2O_2 reaction within seconds. In a reaction mixture containing H_2O_2 $10^{-6} M$ Fe^{II} and known excess of Tl^{III} in HClO_4 solution, H_2O_2 could be known²³ by estimating unreacted Tl^{III} iodometrically. The following is the stoichiometry (15) and mechanism (16-18).

H_2O_2 and Fe^{II} should not be mixed first since Fe^{III} formed through Haber-Weiss mechanism²⁴ is not a catalyst. Fe^{III} works through reduction to Fe^{II} only when it is more than $10^{-4} M$. In any case $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}/\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}$ cycle does not operate. Later it has been said²⁵ that $\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}/\text{HO}_2^*$ cycle works. In any case Fe^{II} should be regarded as a pre-reductor of Tl^{III} to initiate $\text{Tl}^{\text{II}}/\text{HO}_2^*$ or $\text{Tl}^{\text{II}}/\text{O}_2^-$ cycle.

Table 3. Indirect determination of hyponitrite with Ce^{IV} in acid perchlorate solutions and products isolated in the reaction

[Fe^{II}] added = 10 ml of 0.01 mol dm⁻³; titrant, [Ce^{IV}] = 0.00225 mol dm⁻³; vol. of reaction mixture = 100 ml

[HClO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ³ [H ₂ N ₂ O ₂] (mol dm ⁻³)			Found by pp method	Vol. of N ₂ O (ml) ^a	10 ³ [NO ₃] (mol dm ⁻³)
	Taken	Found	Error %			
0.5	5.00	5.08	+1.6		5.3(5.6)	4.90
0.7	5.00	5.03	+0.6		5.0(5.6)	4.92
0.9	5.00	5.00	0.0		5.5(5.6)	4.99
1.0	2.00	2.01	+0.5		2.2(2.2)	1.91
1.1	2.00	2.01	+0.5	1.98	2.1(2.2)	1.91
1.3	4.00	3.96	-1.0		4.2(4.5)	3.80
1.5	4.00	3.96	-1.0		4.1(4.5)	3.90
1.7	5.00	4.80	-4.0		4.5(5.6)	4.50
2.5	5.00	4.50	-10.0		4.0(5.6)	3.25
1.0	1.00	0.975	-0.5	1.10	1.0(1.1)	-
1.0	3.00	3.03	+1.0	3.01	3.4(3.4)	2.91
1.0	4.00	4.01	+0.25	4.02	4.2(4.5)	3.84
1.0	5.00	4.97	-0.5	5.02	5.4(5.6)	4.80

^aValues in parentheses refer to volumes corresponding to eq. (20).

(5) Nature of acid monitoring the reactivity and course of a metal-ion reaction

Reaction of hyponitrous acid (H₂N₂O₂) with Ce^{IV} in H₂SO₄ solutions is a slow process²⁶ and occurs with a stoichiometry (19) and with N₂O, N₂ and HNO₃ as the products.

In an attempt to know more of the mechanism, reaction was carried out in HClO₄ solutions. The reaction was very fast and occurred as (20) with N₂O and HNO₃ as the products.

and this presented a possibility of determining hyponitrite. The results are given in Table 3. Aquo- and hydroxo species of Ce^{IV} seem to be more reactive than sulphate complexes. However, the situation is not that simple since the stoichiometry and the products are different in the two acid solutions. The initial reaction is said to occur as in (21)

followed by the decomposition of H₂N₂O₃ as in (22)

And then further reaction of HNO₂ in two alternative paths as in (23) and (24)

according as there is HClO₄ or H₂SO₄ solution, leading to stoichiometries (20) and (19) respectively. However, it is doubtful whether reaction (24) would occur²⁷ in competence with (23) though there is nothing wrong with the equations (19) and (20).

(6) Modification of known methods to suit a particular kinetic analysis

Examples are no less common where an analytical method has been modified to suit the requirement of following the kinetics of a particular reaction.

The reaction²⁸ of Tl^{III} and As^{III} in HClO₄ solutions occurs as follows

And there seemed to be no method to determine any of the four constituents in the presence of the other three. A

colorimetric method based on iodometry of Tl^{III} with modified conditions was devised. KI less than $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ was employed to check the precipitation of thallos iodide (Tl^I being obtained from the reduction of Tl^{III}). Liberation of iodine from As^V (a product) was checked in low acid medium. On the other hand As^{III} reacts with iodine which could be checked in high acid medium. The suitable acid medium was found to be 2.5–5.0 M HCl and the permissible limit of the concentration of As^V was found to be $5 \times 10^{-4} M$.

There appeared to be no method to determine any constituent independently for following the kinetics of iodate-bromide reaction²⁹.

Phenol was employed to react with iodite and bromine before they could react amongst themselves, and iodate could be iodometrically determined without any interference from the reaction products of phenol. It is known that hypohalites and halites rapidly react with phenol³⁰. $HClO_4$ more than 1.0 M could not be employed since iodate reacts with phenol. Less than 0.2 M $HClO_4$ was not used since the main reaction becomes too slow. Of minor importance is the modification of the method of determination of Fe^{III} for following the kinetics of the reaction³¹ of Fe^{III} with hydroxylamine in acetate buffers.

Fe^{III} was determined by adding a known excess (about four times) of sodium thiosulphate allowing time (1 min) for completion of the reaction, and back titrating excess thiosulphate. This is a modification of the method given by Kolthoff and Tomicek³² which required heating to 60°. The method worked in the present case with large concentration of thiosulphate and giving time for reaction (no heating). The accuracy was better than 0.5%.

(7) Iodine monochloride as a pre-oxidiser in the sulphite-estimation with permanganate

It is only the requirement of a suitable method for following the kinetics which led to the volumetric estimation³³ of sulphite with permanganate, but the more important fact is that the analytical method has enabled one to know the mechanism of the oxidation of sulphite. Sulphite is incompletely oxidized to sulphate (S^{VI}) by permanganate and a fraction of it is oxidized to dithionate which is S^V and which cannot be further oxidized to S^{VI}

by permanganate. If a calculated minimum quantity of iodine monochloride (ICl) as pre-oxidiser is added to the sulphite solution prior to the addition of permanganate, the sulphite solution can be titrated to a sharp end-point to S^{VI} . There are two end-points. The first one, which is orange (due to iodine) should be ignored and the second (yellowish green due to ICl) is final.

Sulphite has a fraction of pyrosulphite which exists in two forms in equilibrium^{34,35}.

(S-S) bond form is preferably oxidized by MnO_4^- and (S-O-S) bond form is preferably oxidized by ICl. Thus if free HSO_3^- is equivalent to y ml of MnO_4^- and (S-O-S) bond form is equivalent to x ml of MnO_4^- , the total sulphite would be equivalent to $(y + x)$ ml of MnO_4^- . This should be the titre if prior addition of ICl is done. If, however, sulphite is directly titrated with MnO_4^- , (without adding ICl), the titre value would be $(y + x/2)$ ml of MnO_4^- as is obvious from (29) below,

Iodine, ICl and iodine all oxidize sulphate to S^{VI} . This sulphite consists of $[SO_3^{2-}]_{\text{free}}$ plus (S-O-S) bond form of pyrosulphite. However, they do not oxidize dithionate. Permanganate oxidizes (S-S) bond form of pyrosulphite to dithionate. Some of these results are given in Table 4.

(B) Contributions of Analytical Chemistry to Kinetics (some aspects)

(1) Greater role of Analytical Chemistry for the evaluation of mechanism

One may appreciate the greater role of Analytical Chemistry in the reaction³¹ of Fe^{III} and NH_3OH^+ in acetate buffers where one has near convincing situation for the mechanism of reaction.

Kinetics does provide reaction scheme, but gives no indication for any complex formation between Fe^{III} and

Table 4. Permanganate oxidation of sulphite in the presence of a minimum quantity (underlined) of iodine monochloride (ICl)

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
10% Sulphite solution ml	Titre with KMnO_4 alone (0.1003 N) ml of MnO_4^-	ICl (0.1 M) ml	First titre for orange color after adding ICl ml of MnO_4^-	Final titre for yellowish green colour ml of MnO_4^-	Difference of column II and V (=pyrosulphite) ml of MnO_4^-
2.0	2.40	1.50 0.90 <u>0.80</u> 0.70 0.60 0.40	1.35 1.91 2.01 2.07 2.14 2.34	2.80 2.80 2.80 2.77 2.75 2.74	0.40
5.0	6.45	2.00 1.50 1.30 <u>1.20</u> 1.10 1.00	5.07 5.50 5.70 5.75 5.79 5.85	7.04 7.045 7.04 7.045 6.85 6.80	0.595
10.0	13.15	2.00 1.90 <u>1.80</u> 1.70 1.50 1.40	12.10 12.15 12.16 12.19 12.25 12.32	14.05 14.06 14.05 13.86 13.76 13.63	0.90
	$y + x/2$	x	y	$y + x$	$x/2$

NH_3OH^+ though there is a possibility. The first key to the mechanism is provided by the fact that the reaction has separate identity for occurring in dark³⁶ and light with different stoichiometries and different gaseous oxidation products of hydroxylamine, though the mechanism is almost same in both cases.

The dark reaction kinetics were followed by measuring the volumes of N_2O gas and the light sensitive reaction was followed by measuring Fe^{III} with thiosulphate. The rate laws and the rates were almost the same.

UV spectroscopy under the two conditions (dark and light) revealed atleast two reactive intermediate complexes which seemed to be kinetically stable. The dark reaction absorption peaks were at 250 nm and 341 nm and ab-

sorbed strongly³⁷. The light sensitive reaction peak was at 290 nm with much less molar extinction coefficient. Kinetics of the decomposition of these complexes was determined by measuring absorption at 341 nm for dark reaction and at 290 nm for the light sensitive reaction. The second order rate constant was $2.4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the dark reaction and $2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for light sensitive reaction at pH 4.05 and 30° which were comparable to the second order rate constant for $2.3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ obtained by volumetric method and $3.7 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (35°) obtained for dark reaction by measuring the volume of the gas. Thus the redox reaction and the decomposition of the intermediate complex were kinetically the same processes.

The biggest push to the mechanism was provided by the fact that the stoichiometry of the two reactions (dark and light sensitive) in the presence of acrylamide was identical and 1 : 1 with no gaseous products. It seems that in the presence of acrylamide, both the reactions are checked at the intermediate redox step. The reaction

scheme (32-33) could be known from the Kinetics which led to the rate law (34).

$$-d[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]/dt = k_1 k_3 [\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] [\text{NH}_3\text{OH}^+] [\text{H}^+] / (k_2 [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}] + k_3 [\text{H}^+]) \quad (34)$$

but the mechanism (details) could be known from UV spectroscopy, variation in the stoichiometry and the solution chemistry for the species³⁸ of Fe^{III} participating in the reaction. The following chart gives the mechanism. It appears that the step (32) of the reaction scheme involves all the steps of the mechanism from 1 of 5/6 and it is here that the reaction stops in the presence of acrylamide.

(2) Existence of iodite

Iodite has not been prepared or isolated. Formation of iodite has always been guessed during the reduction of iodate to hypiodite or iodine. Stoichiometric experiment of the following reaction in the presence of phenol gave indirect evidence²⁹ for the formation of iodite since iodite and bromine reacted with phenol.

There is spectroscopic and thermogravimetric analytical evidence³⁹ in favour of iodite when a mixture of lead and sodium iodate is heated. During a kinetic study⁴⁰ of the oxidation of citric and malonic acids with permanganate in the presence of small concentration of iodide, the reaction mixture even after becoming colourless (no permanganate) contained an iodometric oxidant. A systematic study⁴¹ involving different excess carboxylic acids and ~10⁻² M MnO₄⁻ in the presence of 10⁻³-10⁻⁴ M iodide, always led to an oxidant in the colourless solution, equivalent to four times that of iodide. Similarly if permanganate-oxidised such solutions of carboxylic acids (after becoming colourless) are treated with a solution of ~10⁻³ M iodate, the latter is reduced to its 2/3 oxidant strength. In both cases formation of iodite seems to be a possibility. In the former case it is formed by the oxidation of iodide, and in the second case iodate is reduced. As a matter of fact in both cases, it is a case of reduction of iodate to iodite as shown below.

(i) When iodide is initially added

(ii) When iodate is added and no iodide, steps (35) and (37) occur.

Iodite is stable for hours. It is not known whether any attempt has made to precipitate iodite by the addition of a suitable reagent.

(3) Complexes of increasing reactivity during a kinetic run

Oxidation⁴² of hypophosphite with Tl^{III} is catalysed by chloride ions through the formation of chloro-complexes TlCl²⁺, TlCl₂⁺, TlCl₃ and TlCl₄⁻. The stepwise formation constants in the following reaction are reported⁴³

Table 5. Rate constants of various complexes in the Tl^{III} - H_3PO_2 reactions in the presence of chloride ions at 28°

Reaction	$10^2(\text{rate constant}) M^{-1} s^{-1}$
$Tl^{3+} + H_3PO_2$	$kK = 1.08$
$TlCl^{2+} + H_3PO_2$	$k_1 = 6.7$
$TlCl_2^+ + H_3PO_2$	$k_2 = 2.8$
$TlCl_3 + H_3PO_2$	$k_3 = 12.5$
$TlCl_4^- + H_3PO_2$	$k_4 = 24.0$

to be 5.22×10^6 , 1.25×10^5 , 482 and $65.3 M^{-1}$ (at $I = 0.5 M$ and 25°)

according as $n = 1, 2, 3$ and 4 respectively. Reactivities of various complexes are shown in Table 5. K is formation constant⁴⁴ ($15 M^{-1}$ at 28°) between Tl^{III} and H_3PO_2 in absence of chloride ions and k is the rate constant.

If a kinetic run is planned with almost equivalent concentrations of Tl^{III} and Cl^- , it would not be a normal decrease of Tl^{III} , but as shown in Fig. 2. In the beginning almost whole of Tl^{III} is in 1 : 1 complex. It is completely in that form ($TlCl^{2+}$) after about 40 min. With the passage of time, Tl^{III} decreases and the Cl^- to Tl^{III} ratio increases. The decrease in the rate is compensated by the formation of more reactive $TlCl_2^+$. This formation is complete after about 160 min. Further decrease in Tl^{III} would indicate the formation of $TlCl_3$. Now the decrease in Tl^{III} is more than compensated by the higher reactivity of $TlCl_3$ and the rate increases (the slope of the curve/line increases). This will continue till the whole of Tl^{III} (what-

Fig. 2. A plot showing the course of a single kinetics experiment for the Tl^{III} - H_3PO_2 reaction with $[Tl^{III}]_T = 6.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Cl^-]_T = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[HClO_4] = 1.01 M$ and $[H_3PO_2] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$.

ever it may be) is in the form of $TlCl_4^-$ complex and now the regular rate profile can be seen since there is one reactive form $TlCl_4^-$ and that is decreasing. Thus one single kinetic run enables one to show higher reactivities of successive chloro complexes of Tl^{III} in its reaction with H_3PO_2 in the presence of chloride ions.

(4) Unusual behavior of iodide with regard to its catalysis in the peroxomonophosphoric acid (PMPA) and hydrazine reaction⁴⁵ in acid solution

In general kinetics of the oxidation of hydrazine with any oxidant is followed by determining the oxidant iodometrically and we get into the impression that iodine does not react with hydrazine. It is iodide which in acid medium is oxidized to iodine. In fact this iodine does react with hydrazine for certain range of concentration of iodide. The status of iodide in the presence of an oxidant changes thrice in its concentration range of $\sim 10^{-7}$ to $\sim 10^{-2} M$. It is without any effect if it is less than $\sim 4 \times 10^{-7} M$ since it is present in the form of HOI ^{46,47} (and possibly as IO_3^- and IO_2^-). There is insufficient iodide to convert HOI into iodine, and HOI itself does not react with hydrazine, and so also iodate. Thus in this range of $[I^-]$, free iodine is not available for reaction and catalysis. This becomes available in the concentration range $\sim 4 \times 10^{-7}$ to $\sim 10^{-2} M$. Fig. 3 along with Inset 1 and

Fig. 3. Plot of V_0 vs $[I^-]$ and $[I_2]$ for H_3PO_5 - $N_2H_5^+$ reaction. $[HClO_4] = 0.5 M$ and $I = 2.0 M$. $10^3 [H_3PO_5]$, M and $10^3 [N_2H_5^+]$, M respectively are 2.11 and 2.0 for (O), 1.05 and 2.0 for (●), 2.11 and 1.05 for (Δ) and 2.12 and 2.0 for (×).

Inset 2 show all this in the form of a plot of V_0 or $(-d[\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3]/dt)$ against $[\text{I}^-]$ and $[\text{I}_2]$. The plot of aqueous iodine is a straight line passing through the origin and supports what has been said above. There is no catalysis again if $[\text{I}^-]$ is more than $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ when once again free iodine is not available owing to the formation of I_3^- through the following equilibrium⁴⁸. I_3^- does not react with hydrazine.

There is an optimum concentration of iodide ($4 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$) beyond which there is catalysis (Inset 1) and the cycle I^-/I_2 works. There seems to be a peak-catalysis perhaps at $[\text{I}^-] = \sim 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ and then it decreases (Inset 2). The situation with iodine is simple. The rate increases with the increases of $[\text{I}_2]$, and I_2/I^- cycle operates. This would continue to happen so long iodide is not sufficient to form tri-iodide ion. Free bromine and free chlorine also react with hydrazine and their optimum concentrations for the operation of Br_2/Br^- and Cl_2/Cl^- cycles and catalysis to start are much larger (2×10^{-5} and $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ respectively) and there is no decrease in the rate with the increase of $[\text{Br}^-]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ since equilibrium constants for (40) and (41) are small^{49,50}.

(5) Unusual phenomenon of rate increase during a kinetic run

One reason for this is the successive formation of more reactive species as we have seen in case of Tl^{III} - H_3PO_2 reaction in the presence of chloride ions. Yet another reason is the unusual stoichiometry of the reaction when the mole ratio of a reactant undergoes significant change from an integer to a fraction during a kinetic run. Tl^{III} and thiocyanate react⁵¹ according to the following stoichiometric equation (42).

Three complexes $\text{Tl}_2(\text{SCN})_5^+$ (2 : 1), TlSCN^{2+} (1 : 1) and $\text{Tl}(\text{SCN})_2^+$ (1 : 2) seemed to be formed but only 1 : 1 complex is reactive and its formation constant seemed to be much larger than those for other two complexes. Fig. 4 shows how in the beginning of the reaction $[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}] = 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ is more than $[\text{SCN}^-] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ and less than the stoichiometric excess, but subsequently the decrease in $[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]$ is more than the decrease in $[\text{SCN}^-]$ and a

Reaction of thallium(III) with thiocyanate ion in acid perchlorate solutions

Fig. 4. Plots of the concentrations of Tl^{III} (initially $4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) (O) and SCN^- (initially $2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) (Δ) vs time at $[\text{HClO}_4] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 20° .

situation arises when the mole ratio ($[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]/[\text{SCN}^-]$) decreases from 2 : 1 and 1 : 1 and the whole of Tl^{III} is present as 1 : 1 complex. There is a break in the regularity of the rate-curve at this point (P) and the rate increases because 1 : 1 complex is highly reactive as compared to the other two complexes. Beyond this point there is regular behaviour. Wherever one comes across such situation of stoichiometry and reactivity, one should be able to support the fact that there is an intermediate species which is reactive or much more reactive than the other two, but this would happen only if the formation constant for the intermediate complex is much larger.

The above discussion is just an overview of the subject giving some of aspects of the contributions of Kinetics and Analytical Chemistry to each other. As a matter of fact there would be as many such examples as the number of reactions where one faces difficulty in following the kinetics. Although Analytical Chemistry is useful to Kinetics, it has not been fully and appropriately exploited by the kineticists for the identification of the intermediates and evaluation of the mechanism.

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